

The Impact of Workplace Sexual Harassment among Women and Workplace Ostracism on Personal or Organizational Deviance with the mediating effect of Self-Efficacy

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to find the impact of workplace ostracism and women workplace sexual harassment on the personal or organizational deviance, where the relationship between the variables is mediated through self-efficacy. It moves on the research paradigm of post-positivism where this research creates a new relation among the considered variables. This research was conducted from the private banking sector of Karachi, Pakistan. The data was collected through 245 questionnaires among which best 217 questionnaires were selected for the testing. The data was then passed through the reliability and validity test of SPSS- Smart PLS and all the constructs of the data found to be accurate and reliable while for descriptive statistics and demographical analysis of respondents SPSS statistical tools have been used. This research concludes an insignificant relationship of workplace ostracism with both self-efficacy and personal or organizational deviance, while it found a significant positive relationship of sexual harassment at workplace with both self-efficacy and personal or organizational deviance. This research recommends that the recruitment of supervisors should be based on their leadership skills so they don't ostracize their team members, also good security should be provided to female employees and all the employers should be prohibited to call personal meetings with opposite gender. Furthermore, it provides beneficial knowledge to the students who are studying human resource management and also helpful for the organizations to understand how they can control the deviance in their organization by training their employees to fight against sexual harassment and ostracizers.

Keywords: Workplace Ostracism, Workplace Sexual Harassment, Self-Efficacy

Introduction

In the current era, organizations throughout are somehow investing in developing researches to evaluate why their organizations are lacking output in terms of productivity in employees. The workplace environment is affiliated with the productivity of employees with no gender discrimination. But in this male dominated society, woman is supposed to be a weak and less efficient employee as compared to male employees, this can be a danger to the women career and job satisfaction and can even result in to the disturbance of work-life balance. When organizations don't provide safety measures to their female staff, they eventually weaken their commitment to the organization in return they don't build the level of trust with them and this results in to lack of female staff's self-trust and confidence regarding their professional skills. Knowingly the violence of women rights at the workplace, sexual harassment is the biggest violation of women safety under the premises of the organization and is been raised as a serious issue on several platforms as it is the crucial matter for the organizational satisfactory climate for the employees. According to (Nauman & Abbasi, 2014), sexual harassment is a sort of bullying against women that may lead to serious health and mental problems to the victim and may lead to a loss of organizational productivity or employee turnover in which the organization might lose their most effective female employees who were creative and innovative in the decision making. For any firm, deviant behaviors are a threat to damage its good will or well-being of its all stakeholders that act as the biggest internal obstacle in achieving organizational goals as a team, basically the deviance among

employees occurs when their expectations and the rules of organization don't match which leads employees to involve in such activities beyond the rules and code of conduct in order to fulfill their expectations with the system (Aksu, 2016). When the hierarchy fails to satisfy its employees, they should work for their self-betterment in order to achieve the unbiased behavior from their bosses but instead if they gather hatred and antipathy against their employees, it establishes a sense of betrayal among them which gradually comes out in the form of aggression and deviant behaviors which may involve lying to their subordinates, cheating, fraud, harassment, strike against the system or theft from the organization and it may also include spreading rumors among peers to fulfill aggressive attitude (Robinson & Bennett, 1995). Most of the corruption from employees occurs under the rage of being left out and treated unfair as compare to their peers. It might happen due to class, sex, race, complexion or personal preferences of the employers, when preferences are given to employees on these bases instead of performance measurements then employees tend to get attention from employers through false statements, rumors and lying about their performance, also unjustified behavior of employers create a demonization factor among its workers because they know their efforts for the organization will not be appreciated as much as other employees are admired for their little inputs. An ostracizing employer is the root of creating apathetic feelings among workers through hurting self-respect and neglecting their endeavors in optimizing the output. Here comes the stability of personal traits of the employees, if the ostracized employee is stable and calm enough to tackle workplace favoritism from employers then this injustice may lead him to work harder and trust in his competency to fight back with an improved version of his skills that his boss cannot ignore which will later result in polishing his undiscovered skills or hidden creativity at the workplace due to resilient characteristic in his personality, this implies that it depends on the person's fight or flight nature that decides whether workplace ostracism is going to increase deviance behaviors and violation of organizational norms or whether it will result in improvisation of employee's weak points through establishing a sense of competition. The workplace environment is collectively a field of difficulties parallel to need fulfillments, the employees have to deal with continuous stress to perform better and get increment in their job perks, among these difficulties sexual harassment and equal gender rights is the most common issue faced by several employees that damages their focus in achieving the assigned target. Workplace sexual harassment is the most usual activity that is practice in almost every other firm worldwide where sometimes are also involved in this activity to give sexual favors to the employer in greed of promotion, employers harass the employees by inveigling them to give benefits in shift timings, easier job tasks and giving them favors of providing job security in exchange of sexual favors. Even if the employee is not willing to do so, employers or peers harass them by creating a fear of job loss in their minds, this can be managed with excellence if the employee is trained to protect his self-esteem by raising a voice against such subordinates and believe in his or her skills to achieve the tasks without any kind of favor from peers. Workplace sexual harassment is experienced mostly by female workers and for that reason, the opinions of female respondents in survey would be essential to give final conclusions about the outcomes of deviant behaviors in relative sector of this research Christopher & Amy, (2004). As it had been a major workplace obstacle since decades but still a lot of harassed employees don't have courage to speak out against this practice (Siegel, 2003), and for that reason #me_too movements have been initiated by social workers worldwide since last five years to spread awareness of power to speak up for justice and equal gender rights in the workplace. In United States of America, U.S. Senate in February'22 passed the bill to ban companies who avert employee to file case against harassment during work by any employer or subordinate (Kanu, 2022). Due to sexual harassment, employee's productivity is declined if he or she does not have well defined self-efficacy, in such severe cases of sexual assault employee has to change his or her career and face some serious trauma in exchange of speaking out. Many cases are still not lodged to authorities because employees are oppressed to earn income for their families, thus they give preference to gain better position in exchange of sexual favors. For that reason, victims should be ensured about their job security and protection through higher authorities to motivate their self-efficacy to fight back against such assault of their self-respect because if these issues of ostracizing or neglecting an employee's effort and sexual harassment cases are not addressed in time, this may lead a firm to suffer internally in terms of lesser productivity, poor environment, lesser job satisfaction, increased employee turnover (Houle, Staff, Mortimer, Uggan, &

Blackstone, 2011) and externally in terms of damaged wellbeing, loss of stakeholders and failure to survive in the competition. Therefore, this research is contributing to shed light on one of the major aspects under the organizational activities which lead to destroy the environment of the firm for its workers, discussing the unethical norms of harassment and ostracism at the workplace that lead to create deviant behavior in the organizations. It also contributes to find out how the self-efficacy is playing the role of mediation between the required variables.

An era where organizations cannot work without employees working together with other subordinates, there workplace holds a significant importance to be measured with organizational code of conduct. The team work among members usually comes up with crucial aspects to getting mutually creative ideas and builds a stronger level of communication and control in the organization, but anything that has pros must have some cons too. Similarly when a team establishes for the assigned tasks in the workplace, their interpersonal relationship develops which might sometime leads to grudges among peers which can be driven in any form. Most commonly, it is present in form of biasness and boss's inclination towards their favorite employees that results some negative impacts of developing interpersonal relationship at workplace (Robinson, O'Reilly, & Wang, 2013). This biasness and ignorance to targeted employee reaches out to different negative reactions from that ostracized employee for instance withdrawal from job, fake reports about performance, back biting an increasing absenteeism, loss of interest in group projects or absence of mind at workplace which builds an unhealthy environment at workplace by breeding an unfair competition among employees to beat the rival by hook or by crook (Chung, 2015; O'Reilly & Robinson, 2009). The feeling of an employee about being removed from a group and left over negatively influences the Maslow's hierarch of needs as he presents belongingness to be an important factor in an humans' life survival (William, 2001), this initiates the loss of hope in an employee and he starts assuming that this ostracism has become out of control and cannot be ameliorated by any means or efforts forming a meaningless presence of one's role, named as "social death" by (Sommer, Williams, Ciarocco, & Baumeister, 2004). But it is not necessary that someone gets ignored intentionally, may be the boss or subordinate is too busy to react to one's performance or ignores an employee without any purpose and boss has no idea that he is excluding an employee (Robinson, O'Reilly, & Wang, 2013), which indicates that ostracizer is not always aware of his actions of degrading an employee (Sommer, Williams, Ciarocco, & Baumeister, 2004) therefore ostracized employees should be trained well to manage in such situations at workplace and do not feel demotivated by subordinates' behavior instead of working honestly for their own job role (Woon & Ji Yeon, 2017). Besides, ostracism, harassment is another active element in the workplace that damages the mental health of employees; this can be almost obscure and not prominent to the employee who is being eventually harassed. For instance, touching the shoulder of peers, staring at them, commenting on their attires, complimenting their looks or appearance in an absolute absurd manner that makes an employee simply uncomfortable is the basic sexual harassment while sometimes this harassment is open invitation to subordinates for pre-mentioned sexual favors which is quite obvious to other employees as well determining an unsound environment within the premises of an organization. When firms don't invest in making policies for secure healthy workplace conditions, it results in negative outcomes as in job related side effects and poor work experience, simultaneously augmenting lower productivity in its workforce and loss of committed employees (Willness, Steel, & & Lee, 2007). For such vulnerable activities, victims seek usually two ways as a coping strategy, either they accept the offer and gain advantages by the subordinates or they quit their job silently or by complaining their discomfort through raising voice at workplace which eventually catalyzes the chances of job loss or threatening situations. Thus, it is the primary responsibility of employer to conduct regular open end questionnaire based surveys in which employees or any sort of victims can update the employer about any illegal or immoral activity going within his establishment (Shaw, Hegewisch, & Hess, 2018). Further, another most important factor in this context is building self-efficacy among employees to empower them with their competencies and trust in their skills to initiate their actions for organization's benefits without any sort of fear from subordinates. This factors belongs to employees' persistency when they face challenging workplace conditions, the higher they believe in themselves, the higher they can persist such challenges at workplace (Geraghty, 2013). In contrary, if they are not enough stable to cope with any uncertain situation, their instability

may beget rebelliousness in them against the system and their need to fulfill independence and self-esteem may open doors to indulge in deviant behaviors for dodging and illicit schemes at workplace. Therefore, the research has understood the importance and background of this relationship and has found that workplace ostracism and sexual harassment should be studied together in finding their influence on deviant workplace behaviors from victims' side in presence of self-efficacy in the private banking sector of Pakistan.

Workplace Ostracism

Workplace ostracism has been identified from past two decades, defining the circumstances where an employee gets overlooked and neglected by other employees (Choi, 2020; Ferris, Brown, Berry, & Lian, 2008), this workplace atmosphere forefronts the major causes of incomplete tasks (Abbas, Darr, & Bouckennooghe, 2014; Jamal, 1985; Ng & Feldman, 2012; Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019) as to carry out the expected outcomes, positive attitude at the workplace is the basic need but the poor behaviors and ignorance of subordinates tend to create hazards for the employees to meet the objectives of the organization (Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019; Eisenberger, Armeli, Rexwinkel, Lynch, & Rhoades, 2001; Hussain & Asif, 2012; Khurram, 2009). Despite, workplace ostracism does not only leads to the cons for organization, but it also cannot be harmful for some employees depending on their personal traits of coping up with the subordinates who overlook them (Wu, Yim, Kwan, & Zhang, 2012; Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019; Liu, Kwan, Lee, & Hui, 2013), being a part of the group meeting, relying on their personal skills they can showcase their self-belief (Jones, Carter-Sowell, Kelly, & Williams, 2009) against their peers instead of losing trust in their qualifications and knowledge (Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019). The feeling of being oppressed and neglected by surrounding people is the extreme disheartening emotion (Scott, Tams, Schippers, & Lee, 2015) that may even result in suicidal thoughts among victims which is the true indicator of depression and declined mental stability (Chen, Poon, DeWall, & Jiang, 2020). From the study of (O'Reilly & Robinson, 2009) it was found that almost 71% of surveyed employees identified themselves as the victims at their workplace which determines the seriousness and significance of highlighting this prevailing issue in most of the organizations worldwide.

Workplace Sexual Harassment

The word "harassment" leads to the means of sexually demeaning a person to fulfill one's sexual desires against the code of conduct. Similarly, (Shetty & V, 2017) describes the workplace harassment as an unwanted attitude towards employees which can cause a cost of low self-esteem, lack in punctuality, increased absences, lowered productivity, an increased rate of employee turnover, costs the firms for the lawsuits and loss of life and social status (Dos, Kumar, & Pavan, 2014). Similarly, (Johnson, Widnall, & Benya, 2018) quoted workplace sexual harassment as a sexual request which may be verbally or non-verbally effect the employment of the employee in case of refusal to the employer's requested favors, which creates an objectionable work environment. This hazard is quite commonly faced by women workers and was first identified when women lost their jobs due to sexual demands of their employers in Barnes v. Train (1974) incident naming it as a do or die situation for the females where their job is hanged on the conditions of fulfilling sexual requirements of the employees (Johnson, Widnall, & Benya, 2018). This harassment does not only harms the victim but also hurts the subordinates resulting in the form of preferences on the bases of employers' desired women employee by appointing them on upper posts, increasing salaries and bonuses which discriminates other employees and eventually they begin to feel unappreciated for their efforts (Roscigno, 2019; McBrier & Wilson, 2004; Wilson, 1997). In Pakistan, this problem is arising day by day in the forms of staring, unwanted touching and intentional lesser physical distance (Anila, 1998). Today, this issue is asking for some serious attention in every workplace presenting the figure of 1.7 million tweets from all over the world (Park, 2017) and 12 million posts on Facebook (Gillaspie, 2018) in a day against women sexual harassment which is an absolute measure to look up for this problem in the offices and all workplaces in order to provide a safer workplace to the female employees.

Self-Efficacy

This terminology defines one's self-belief on his/her own abilities to compete and shine brighter than the subordinates (Yusuf, 2011), how a certain employee portrays himself in different circumstances and keeps

himself motivated and have faith in himself to accept the challenges and take exceptions (Wilde & Hsu, 2019; Bandura, Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change, 1977). Whenever, they encounter being side-tracked, they can learn from what they are lacking immediately and improve themselves for future incidents, but if they lack self-trust, their self-efficacy would decline due to setbacks they are facing and this results in their decreased productivity and hatred among subordinates which leads a deviant behavior in the employees (Bandura, Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change, 1977). This capability of self-assessment is the best practice to increase personal abilities in order to cope up with the distractions and stress created by the employers and subordinates. We understand that self-efficacy is not connected with the means of self-worth but with the self-esteem and confidence in one's self-abilities to face the situations with a firm self-belief of optimism. This concept was identified by (Bandura, 1977) who presented the social cognitive theory to develop a better understanding of social learning to fulfill the need of belongingness and esteem. The self-efficacy should be trained with proper instruction and stable mindsets, if it exceeds the expectations then it may be cause of disaster sometimes, like overestimation of one's skills is the dark side of self-efficacy for instance consider a marathon player who has blind trust in his running skills and is sure of winning the race but due to lack of training he gets injured in the middle of the marathon and end up losing the challenge (Zulkosky, 2009). This indicates that self-efficacy should never be go beyond one's actual capability but if proper guidance is given to the employee he can make the best of his skills in coping with sudden situations. A well-polished self-efficacy in an employee determines motivation and higher productivity in accomplishing assigned work-related job tasks efficiently (Abun, Nicolas, Apollo, Magallanes, & Encarnacion, 2021) that is improved mainly by four experiences identified by (Lopes-Garrido, 2020) which include performance results, watched experiences, boosted self-belief through positive feedbacks and psychological emotional or stability.

Personal or Organizational Deviance

This term is used for the organizations who are involved in unethical moralities within (Aksu, 2016; Ermann & Lundman, 1978). Being a hazard between organizational goals and deviant behavior of the employees, organizational deviance can be considered as a discrepancy in the way of organization's success and its moralities for abiding the terms and code of conduct by disregarding the subordinates which may lead to create unsatisfactory work conditions for other employees. (Aksu, 2016) mentions the norms of organizational deviance from the studies of (Demir, 2009; O'Neill, Lewis, & Carswell, 2011) which involves misleading, false statements, harassment, absenteeism, embezzlements and theft under the premises of the organization. It also results in flowing the confidential information out of the firm through the unofficial personnel who are not certified as beholders of such information (Zhang, Chen, & Chen, 2008; Aksu, 2016). Organizational deviance has a direct negative relationship with ethical leadership which leads to the fact that the more the leaders tend to be supportive towards the employees, the more the organization can be saved from deviant behavior (Liao, Joshi, & Chuang, 2004).

Problem Statement

Workplace sexual harassment is an issue which is not openly expressed by the victims due to the fear of job loss (Shetty & V, 2017) resulting the traumatic experiences more for the women employees (Johnson, Widnall, & Benya, 2018). This leads to interpersonal conflict and loss of productivity, inability to participate in the meetings due to absence of mind, decreased self-confidence, fear of challenges and disturbed work-life balance (Visinskaite, 2015). Whereas, apart from workplace sexual harassment, workplace ostracism is also found as the cause of decreased self-efficacy (Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019) due to lack of appreciations and being leftover by subordinates makes an employee feel not compatible for the competencies required for the desired output (Lima, 2018; Sarwar, Abdullah, Sarfraz, & Imran, 2019; Chen & Li, 2019). Furthermore, (Kura, Faridawahti, & Chauhan, 2015) we also found that when self-efficacy is increased then eventually organizational deviance is controlled which depicts a relation between the self-efficacy and organizational deviance, concluding to a fact that to control organizational deviance, firms need to evaluate personality traits

in their employees to find out their mental stabilities to face such behaviors from their subordinates . Another research (Jahanzeb & Fatima, 2018) proves that when employees feel excluded from the groups, feel unappreciated and are sexually harassed, they grow interpersonal deviance within themselves which leads them to endanger the wellbeing of other members (Samiullah, 2019). So, from the study of the past research work on the required variables, we found that both the workplace sexual harassment and ostracism are effecting self-efficacy of employees and also causing organizational deviance, that's why this research will move further to find out whether self-efficacy is playing the role of mediation or not, and what kind of relation it forms between the independent and the dependent variables of this research.

Significance

This research is conducted under the private banking sector of Pakistan, which provides an understanding of how workplace ostracism is common in our banking sector, especially workplace sexual harassment on women is causing a deviant behavior in the female employees (Waseem, 2016). It provides the idea that our banking sector needs to control ostracism and harassment in order to increase self-efficacy among employees.

Research Questions

1. Which practices are involved in workplace ostracism?
2. What are the effects of workplace sexual harassment on women?
3. What leads to organizational deviant behavior?
4. Why an employee lacks self-efficacy?

Research Objectives

- O₁: To find out the impact of workplace ostracism on self-efficacy.
- O₂: To find out the impact of workplace ostracism on personal or organizational deviance.
- O₃: To find out the impact of workplace sexual harassment on self-efficacy.
- O₄: To find out the impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance.
- O₅: To find out the impact of self-efficacy on personal or organizational deviance.

Scope

1. This research will be beneficial for the students to get help in their researches related to human resource activities.
2. This research will be helpful for the organizations to understand how they can reduce deviant behavior in their firms.
3. This research can be a guide for all the organizations who want to enhance their performance and are seeking for the human resource department to do so.
4. This research will be helpful Pakistani private banking sector to understand how to prevent workplace sexual harassment and workplace ostracism.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no impact of workplace ostracism on personal or organizational deviance with the mediation of self-efficacy.

H_{A1}: There is the impact of workplace ostracism on personal or organizational deviance with the mediation of self-efficacy.

H₀₂: There is no impact of workplace ostracism on personal or organizational deviance without the mediation of self-efficacy.

H_{A2}: There is the impact of workplace ostracism on personal or organizational deviance without the mediation of self-efficacy.

H₀₃: There is no impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance with the mediation of self-efficacy.

H_{A3}: There is the impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance with the mediation of self-efficacy.

H₀₄: There is no impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance without the mediation of self-efficacy.

H_{A4}: There is the impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance without the mediation of self-efficacy.

Literature Review

Workplace Ostracism and Self-Efficacy

Also, (Dirk, Haq, & Azeem, 2019) presented a negative relation between workplace ostracism and self-efficacy in their research as it was found that employees who had experienced the workplace ostracism tend to be less productive and were failed to meet the desired output for the given tasks. When employees are appreciated and involved in discussions, they become confident on their competencies. Due to ostracized behaviors, employees feel that their skills and innovative ideas are not welcomed and they are not wanted as a required entity towards organizational success this decreases a sense of belongingness and commitment with the organization and also decreases the self-efficacy or self-esteem of the ostracized employee (William, 2001), these increased poor interactions will bring a decline in self-trust of employees (Ferris, Brown, Berry, & Lian, 2008). The *Conservation of Resources Theory* (COR) was found to be associated with self-efficacy and workplace ostracism while focusing on job stress according to (Sarwar, Abdullah, Sarfraz, & Imran, 2019) where they concluded that due to increased workplace ostracism, employees feel the loss of their emotional resource of self-efficacy due to being pushed back from the employers and this brings severe mental disturbance to the victimized employees at the workplace. In a study from (Mikkelsen & Einarsen, 2002) as cited by (Hsieh, Wang, & Ma, 2019), self-efficacy is a moderator for the impact of workplace ostracism on psychological health issues of employees, quoting that bullying is a practice that causes severe health traumas including stress, anxiety, loss of concentration, decline in productivity, less participation and interactions due to lack of confidence and trust in their personal and professional skills to present themselves as a competent employee as compared to the peers or subordinates. In another study from (Cakirpaloglu, Čech, & Kvintova, 2018), they found that the teacher's personal traits and performance is being significantly affected by the violent approaches of bullying in the schools quoting mobbing as the serious issue under workplace ostracism, they found that due to bullying of elementary teachers their self-esteem is declined and they lose the confidence on their teaching skills while those teachers who were never bullied were found with no negative impact on their self-efficacy. While (Fatima, Ilyas, Rehman, & Imran, 2017) mentioned the study of (Morrison, 2014) to quote that workplace ostracism leads a person to feel pessimistic, ignored and unacknowledged for his efforts due to which they develop the fear of idea sharing to defend themselves for further bullying and humiliation due to which their self-efficacy does not allow them to be a highlighted employee and they appreciate defensive silence which causes the organizations to lack creativity and innovation. Therefore, for a successful and competitive organization, it is necessary to endorse creativity among employees and enhance their self-efficacy through continuous appreciations, acknowledgments and sharing the decision making ideas with them so they feel valued and give their best commitment to the organization considering organizational success as the common shared goal. Also, self-efficacy can reduce the stress caused by workplace ostracism as women tend to be more stressful due to being ignored and leftover (Sarwar, Abdullah, Sarfraz, & Imran, 2019). The employees with more self-efficacy are less effected from the negative behaviors of the subordinates. Ostracism is not the only cause for the lack self-efficacy but also the cultural differences, language proficiencies, way of living and dressing sense can also be the measures on which an employee evaluates himself (Lima, 2018). An increment in the workplace ostracism leads to deduction of the victimized employee's resources and may result in the increased turnover rate for the organization (Fiset, Al-Hajj, & Vongas, Workplace Ostracism Seen through the

Lens of Power, 2017). From previous contribution in literature of this relation, the researcher establishes the first hypothesis of this research to find a significant impact of workplace ostracism on self-efficacy.

Workplace Ostracism and Personal or Organizational Deviance:

Moreover, according to a research conducted in a public sector of Pakistan (Samiullah, 2019), it was found that in the workplace environment of Pakistan, there is more probability of employees to be ostracized by acknowledged the previous researches that due to lack of professionalism, employees tend to increase deviant behavior instead of finding a way to represent the issue in case of biasness and ostracism. Another research concluded that leaders' mistreatment, employee hostility, intention to quit, mental stress, low self-confidence, work-life conflict and all the other effects of workplace ostracism and sexual harassment have a positive effect on interpersonal as well as organizational deviance among harassed and ostracized employees (Waseem, 2016). When an employee is being ostracized they lead to deviant behaviors at the workplace due to emotional aspects and defensive silence as emotional exhaustion is also a mediator for the impact of workplace ostracism on deviance in the organizations (Jahanzeb & Fatima, 2018) where emotional exhaustion is described by (Yoo, 2013) from the study of (Maslach, Christina, & Susan, 1981) as a feeling of being weighed down or overloaded by an unwanted exposure to something and a sensation of being emotionally "drained" (Cropanzano, 1998) and due to being emotionally weak and lack of self-trust and confidence, they may become pessimistic for their efforts due to disrupted environment with the subordinates or employers and indulge into deviant behaviors at the workplace (Donahue, Forest, Vallerand, Lemyre, Braud, & Bergeron, 2012). Similarly, (Chung & Yang, 2017) also quoted a significant positive impact of workplace ostracism on interpersonal and organizational deviance where the relation was found to be mediated with the self-efficacy of employees, concluding that due to stress and humiliation caused by ostracizes' poor behavior and mistreatment, the self-efficacy of employees is destroyed and they become demotivated and endorse hatred among the peers and subordinates, due to which the common goal sharing of success between employees and organization gets disregarded and as a result employees tend to move for deviant behaviors in order to fulfill their demands or they become deviant in forms being absent-minded at work and lack of interest in the group discussions and team works. The ostracism at the workplace is another form of domestic violence but without any physical and verbal harms to the employees, it can be referred as cold violence (Ferris, Brown, Berry, & Lian, 2008; Jiang, Jiang X, Sun, & Li, 2020) which results in declined commitment and promising relationship of employees with their organization (Jahanzeb & Fatima, 2018). When employee's productivity is harmed it eventually directly creates negative impact on the organization's service performance and they begin to indulge deviant traits in their workplace behavior (Peng & Zeng, 2017), but it is not necessary in the case of all employees due to their individual skills to deal with stressing environment of the workplace (Enwereuzor, Onyishi, Onyebueke, Amazue, & Nwoke, 2017; Hitlan, 2009). In this scenario, *Transactional Model of Stress and Coping Theory* (TMSC) can present the insignificant impact of workplace ostracism on deviant behavior (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) which quotes that trait of resilience among emotionally strong employees makes them vulnerable among biasness and unjustified behavior of their subordinates and they tend to build coping strategies against ostracism instead of becoming a rebel with a cause in the organization and feel victimized (Hao, Hong, Xu, Zhou, & Xie). Thus, the second hypothesis of this research is established to find significant impact of workplace ostracism on interpersonal or organizational deviance.

Workplace Sexual Harassment and Self Efficacy:

Since self-efficacy is developed by our childhood experiences in which we develop a sense of positive interaction with others that is resulted in the well-being of a person (Rosenberg, 1965), similarly employees' self-esteem may be harmed when they experience sexual harassment and bullying on their personal or professional weaknesses which may lead to deviant behaviors in order to prevent one's self esteem (Alexander, 2007) Due to male psychology as they consider women sexual harassment as a source of having control over women (Dannenbaum & Jayaram, 2005), this leads to sever mental loss in terms of lack of concentration, stress, anxiety and decrease of self-efficacy in the victimized employees. The self-efficacy is the main component of

Bandura's social cognitive theory, where people make assumptions of their own skills and traits and tend to bring adaptations according to environmental requirements or actions for achieving their desired results. This definition relates workplace deviant behaviors and self-efficacy to the *Social Cognitive Theory* (SCT) which describes the influences of individual experiences, environmental factors and actions of others which bring changes in a person's behavior due to self-efficacy of changing one's behavior and expectation of the desired outcome due to changes in behavior (Bandura, Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory, 1986). Further, (Visinskaite, 2015) provided enough evidence of a significant negative relationship of workplace bullying and harassment with the self-esteem of employees. Bullying or sexual harassment causes mental stress, health disabilities, decreased life satisfaction which results in the declination of one's self-efficacy.

Workplace Sexual Harassment and Personal or Organizational Deviance:

In a research (Paracha & Shahzad, 2017) concluded that bullying involving harassment results as the deviant behavior in nurses, depicting a positive relation between workplace harassment and organizational deviance, also mentioned interpersonal conflict as a mediator that effects the deviant behavior in a positive relationship. In the context of workplace deviant behaviors, employees become deviant in response to individual experiences of being bullied, harassed, discourteously treated and organizational unjustified environment because they assume that they can achieve what they want in the organization through their deviant behaviors at the workplace. These behaviors can be on the organizational level or either interpersonal level (Aquino, Lewis, & Bradfield, 1999), organizational deviant behavior is the violation of organizational conduct and harming its structure through threatening practices which are generally referred as property deviance including destruction of office equipment and property stealing while interpersonal deviant practices include bullying, sexual harassment, absenteeism, working slowly (Howladar, Rahman, & Uddin, 2018), this shows a positive impact of lack of self-efficacy on increased deviant behaviors at the workplace in case of emotionally weak employee. Bullying or harassment creates a sense of being discriminated and leads to cause stress among the harassed employees, to prevent this, hiring should be done on fair bases by testing all the personality aspects of the candidates (Malik, Sattar, Younas, & Nawaz, 2019). (Ahmad & Omar, 2013) defined organizational deviance as a damage to the image of organization, concluded that due to harassment, an employee indulges in work-family conflict which results in the employee's involvement in deviant behavior for the organization. When employees feel outraged due to stressors at workplace, their betrayal against organization is the most possible outcome of sexual harassment (Colbert, Mount, Harter, Witt, & Barrick, 2004; Schat & Kelloway, 2005) employees who are sexually harassed begin to blame their firms for repeated lack of control over harassing disturbance from their subordinates and then they counterattack to their behavior by getting involved in interpersonal and organizational deviant behaviors to reciprocate the harm to their dignity (Willness, Steel, & Lee, 2007). The sexual assault on employees generate stressful performance that has severe psychological effects on their health and induces resentment among them which further emerges as different terms of violence against organizational conduct that hurts firm's accomplishments as a team (Tepper, Henle, Lambert, Giacalone, & Duffy, 2008). Therefore, the researcher tends to find significant impact of workplace sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance among employees.

Self-Efficacy and Personal or Organizational Deviance:

In literature, (Kura, Faridawahti, & Chauhan, 2015) concluded that if the personality traits should be tested at the time of recruitment to evaluate their tendency to cope up with misbehaving subordinates, in order to find out the level of self-efficacy in the employees. The more the employees are emotionally stable, the more the organizational deviance can be controlled, which shows a negative relationship between self-efficacy and organizational deviance. Furthermore, (Ahmad & Safaria, 2013) quoted self-efficacy as an optimistic approach towards self-belief concluding their research with a significant positive relationship between task completion and self-efficacy. Those participants who had better self-confidence gained higher performance than those who had lack of self-confidence. Self-efficacy has a direct impact on achievement motivation as the person with

higher self-efficacy is enough capable of trust his competencies to bring out the desired output (Yusuf, 2011). While, employees who don't have faith in their abilities develop deviant behavior in return to their leader's mistreatment, they start creating hatred against others and get involved in unethical norms which may lead the firm to be involved immoral activities (Thau, Workman, Dijke, & Cremer, 2011) . In order to connect with the minds of employees, employers need to create a friendly environment in the firm so that employees can feel enough confident to share their experiences with the employers rather than provoking deviant behavior within themselves.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework:

Methodology

Research Design: The research paradigm of this research is Post-Positivism which presents a new relation between the four variables under consideration. This research is a one-time cross-sectional study.

Research Variables: In this research, workplace ostracism and sexual harassment are considered as independent variables and personal or organizational deviance as dependent variable; while self-efficacy is considered as the mediating variable in the relation.

Sampling Technique and Data Collection: The participants of this research are chosen through random sampling technique from private banking sector of Karachi. This research is conducted from 245 respondents among which the best 217 questionnaires are accepted for the sample data with the minimal exposure of the researcher with the respondents.

Statistical techniques and tools: The questionnaires had a format of liker scale that includes the value as 5 for strongly agree, 4 for Agree, 3 for Neutral, 2 for Disagree and 1 for strongly disagree. The data is then found reliable through the validity and reliability tests of SPSS-Smart PLS, where composite reliability, Rho-A and Chronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the reliability of the data. For further descriptive statistics and demographical information of respondents, SPSS has been used to analyze questionnaires.

Results

**and
Analysis**

Figure 2: Research Model

Construct Reliability and Validity

Table 1
Chronbach's Alpha , Rho_A & Composite Reliability

	Chronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Personal or Organizational Deviance	0.819	0.828	0.881	0.65
Self-Efficacy	0.936	0.937	0.954	0.838
Workplace Sexual Harassment	0.844	0.856	0.888	0.710
Workplace Ostracism	0.885	0.886	0.917	0.701

The constructs of the data are found consistent from the table 1, where all the values of Chronbach's alpha are fulfilling the requirements of reliability of the data as according to (Uzhakina, 2007; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011 ; Altman & Head, 1997; Taber, 2016) the data is highly acceptable and accurate when its Chronbach's alpha is higher than or equal to 0.7 .Similary, (Tarkkonen & I., 2005) found that a data is reliable when its Rho-A is higher then or equal to 0.7 while (Borsboom, 2004; Raykov, 1997) proposed the reliability and acceptance of the data if its composite reliability is greater than 0.7. So, according to these measures , all the constructs are highly acceptable and reliable for this research.

Discriminant Validity

If the discriminant validity of a data is confirmed it means that each construct of the data is different from the other construct. This discriminant validity is based on three criterions which include Cross-loading factors,

Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) correlation ratio (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2014). Following are the tables which confirm the validity of the data for this research.

Table 2
Factor Loading

	Personal or Organizational Deviance	Self-Efficacy	Workplace Harassment	Workplace Ostracism
POD1	0.811	0.598	0.223	0.148
POD2	0.86	0.555	0.281	0.194
POD3	0.83	0.551	0.324	0.225
POD4	0.717	0.424	0.357	0.318
SE1	0.629	0.944	0.286	0.233
SE2	0.65	0.913	0.282	0.21
SE3	0.589	0.902	0.3	0.301
SE4	0.563	0.903	0.257	0.26
WPH1	0.278	0.321	0.656	0.802
WPH2	0.172	0.109	0.701	0.488
WPH3	0.292	0.253	0.845	0.396
WPH4	0.347	0.24	0.858	0.468
WPH5	0.275	0.216	0.843	0.571
WPO1	0.165	0.212	0.512	0.918
WPO2	0.177	0.207	0.461	0.866
WPO3	0.216	0.213	0.557	0.878
WPO4	0.192	0.191	0.407	0.839
WPO5	0.295	0.265	0.806	0.626

In table 2, since all the values of Factor-Loadings are higher than 0.7 with its own construct and lesser than 0.7 with other constructs therefore the data passes the first test of discriminant validity (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2014). Moreover, the factor loading value of every construct with its own latent construct is higher than the values with other latent constructs, thus it shows that all variables are discriminant and different from each other.

Table 3
Fornell & Larcker criterion

	Personal or Organizational Deviance	Self-Efficacy	Workplace Harassment	Workplace Ostracism
Personal or Organizational Deviance	0.806			
Self-Efficacy	0.665	0.916		
Workplace Harassment	0.362	0.308	0.785	
Workplace Ostracism	0.267	0.273	0.704	0.832

After passing the cross-loading, the data is tested through Fornell-Larcker criterion, in which the square root of the AVE is compared with the correlation of the latent constructs. Every construct explains its variance of each indicator better than the variances of other latent constructs (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2014). In the Table 3, we see that the square root of each construct’s AVE is larger than the correlation values of other constructs, this proves that the variance of every construct is explaining its own construct better than others due to which the collected passed the discriminant validity from Fornell-Larcker criterion.

Table 4***Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) Ratio of Correlation***

	Personal or Organizational Deviance	Self-Efficacy	Workplace Harassment	Workplace Ostracism
Personal or Organizational Deviance				
Self-Efficacy	0.753			
Workplace Harassment	0.427	0.326		
Workplace Ostracism	0.305	0.29	0.756	

The last measure of discriminant validity testing is Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlation. This method gives the specificity and sensitivity rates up to 97% to 99% which are higher as compared to cross loading i.e. 0.00% and Fornell-Larcker criterion i.e. 20.82% (Barney, 1991). The threshold value of HTMT ratio is 0.85 which means that the more the value of HTMT is closer to 1, the more it lacks the discriminant validity in the data (Rabbi, Ahad, Kousar, & Ali, 2015), and the values closer to 0 portray the presence of discriminant validity among all the constructs of the data. In table 4.2.3, we see that the collected data fulfill all the measures of HTMT ratio that's why the data is highly acceptable and valid to find the relationship between the variables of this research.

Demographics	F	%	Demographics	F	%
<i>Gender ></i>			<i>Income Group ></i>		
Male	130	59.9%	Below 20,000	0	0%
Female	87	40.1%	20,000-30,000	22	10.1%
			30,000-40,000	114	52.5%
			40,000-50,000	64	29.5%
<i>Age ></i>			50,000-60,000	8	3.7%
21 to 25 years	2	0.9%	Above 60,000	9	4.1%
26 to 30 years	59	27.2%			
31 to 35 years	73	33.6%			
36 to 40 years	65	30%			
41 and Above	18	8.3%			
<i>Experience ></i>			<i>Qualification ></i>		
Less than 1 year	57	26.3%	Under Matric	10	4.6%
1-3 years	59	27.2%	Matric	51	23.5%
4-6 years	55	25.3%	Intermediate	79	36.4%
7-9 years	26	12 %	Bachelors	46	21.2%
10 years or above	20	9.2%	Post-Graduate	31	14.3%
*N=217					

Demographic Information

Table 5

In table 5 through SPSS, demographics of the participants has been analyzed by the researcher. In the survey, the ratio between male and female respondents was 60-40 where 130 respondents were male and 87 respondents were female, this shows that the topic of the research has been opinionated by mutual perspectives of both genders, among them 197 respondents were between 26 to 40 years of age, only 2 were below 26 while 18 were above 41 years which predicts that the questionnaires have been answered by mature employees. Further, 26% of respondents had less than 1 year of experience, 57% had 1-3 years , 25% had 4-6 years while 21% had experience of more than 7 years, thus all participants have better understandings of workplace environment. The researcher has also analyzed participants in different income groups to understand the rank levels of respondents where no respondent was found below income of Rs. 20,000 while most of the respondents lied between 30,000 to 50,000 salary, only 22 employees were below 30,000 and 17 respondents were above 60,000 that conforms with their age and experience data. Moreover, only 10 of 217 respondents were under Matric, 51 had done matriculation, while most of the respondents were intermediate, bachelors and post graduates which indicates that respondents had good knowledge and are well-qualified to participate in the survey to conduct this research.

Discussions and Results

The central purpose of this research was to conduct survey in banking sector of Pakistan to study the levels of workplace ostracism and workplace sexual harassment and their influence on explaining personal or organizational deviance when the relationship is mediated by self-efficacy of employees. The researcher has

studied relationship through COR, TMSC and SCT theories where the researcher has analyzed impacts of ostracism and harassment on self-efficacy of respondents under COR and SCT while impacts of self-efficacy on deviant behaviors has been identified under the lights of TMSC Theory. The sample size for survey was selected through random sampling technique for which N=217 respondents were chosen to participate in the survey. Further, the researcher has analyzed the questionnaires through detailed calculations from SMART-PLS and SPSS where reliability and discriminant validity as well as significance of the relations has been analyzed by Smart-PLS bootstrapping technique, for direct and indirect effects of workplace ostracism and sexual harassment on deviant behaviors of employees, the demographics information of participants and the descriptive statistics of questionnaire items is analyzed through SPSS statistics. The detailed multiple regression under mediating effects and direct effect or indirect effects will be discussed later while analyzing coefficient of determination and regressions. The questionnaire was designed as likert scaling and the labeling of values is discussed in methodologies of this research where each both independent variables had 5 items each while mediating and dependent variable had 4 items each to explain them. The items selected to explain workplace ostracism were suggested by (Fiset, Hajj, & Vongas, Workplace Ostracism Seen through the Lens of Power, 2017) that are WPO₁: I feel excluded from team discussions, WPO₂: I never get appreciation for what I do, WPO₃: My skills are usually neglected by my supervisor, WPO₄: My boss don't treat all the team members equally and WPO₅: My ideas are usually rejected. The 5-items selected to explain workplace sexual harassment suggested by (Nielsen, et al., 2019) include WPH₁: I feel uncomfortable around my supervisor, WPH₂: I usually feel unwanted physical contact, WPH₃: I usually get favors from my supervisor without any reason, WPH₄: My supervisor treats me differently when I'm alone and WPH₅: I am usually admired for my physical appearance. While items for measuring self-efficacy were suggested by (Loeb, 2016) which include SE₁: I always express my opinion when my supervisor disagrees with me, SE₂: I trust in my skills, SE₃: I openly speak about my ideas and SE₄: I never compromise my self-respect in any case. Moreover, items for measuring personal or organizational deviance have been suggested from the study of (Agwa, 2018) that are POD₁: I usually act rudely at workplace, POD₂: I usually leave early, POD₃: I usually act sick to get halftime and POD₄: I usually curse my boss with my peers. Further discussions on related results have been mentioned in sections later.

Table 6
Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Workplace Ostracism	217	1.00	5.00	3.7318	0.89015
Workplace Sexual Harassment	217	1.00	5.00	3.6562	0.77577
Self-Efficacy	217	1.00	5.00	3.9044	0.84253
Personal or Organizational Deviance	217	1.00	5.00	3.8537	0.79069

From descriptive statistics analyzed through SPSS statistical software, in the table 6 minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation is mentioned. As mentioned in the chapter of methodologies, the labeling of values are discussed where 1 is labeled for strongly disagree and 5 is labeled for strongly agree. Let's understand the mean values of each variable of this research, the mean of workplace ostracism is 3.73, mean of workplace sexual harassment is 3.65, mean of self-efficacy is 3.90 while mean of personal and organizational deviant behaviors is 3.85. Since 3 is labeled for neutral and 4 is labeled for agree, thus we see all these means are indicating a mean of above 3 and closer to 4 which indicates that most of the respondents have marked to agree to related item and strongly agree for the items of self-efficacy. Moreover, standard deviation displays the dispersion of data from mean. The SD is below 1 that indicates a very low dispersion in data and confirms the reliability of collected opinions. From mean and standard deviation, coefficient of variation for each item is calculated where workplace ostracism has a $CV = 0.238$ i.e. 23.8% ($\sigma = 0.890$, $\mu = 3.7318$), workplace sexual harassment has $CV = 0.2121$ i.e. 21.21% ($\sigma = 0.7757$, $\mu = 3.656$), self-efficacy has $CV = 0.2156$ i.e. 21.56% ($\sigma = 0.842$, $\mu =$

3.9044), while personal or organizational deviance has $CV = 0.2051$ i.e. 20.51% ($\sigma = 0.7906$, $\mu = 3.8537$), all these coefficients of variation indicate that the data has very low variance from mean and the data is highly acceptable for this research,

Table 7
Significance Test

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
Self-Efficacy_ -> Personal or Organizational Deviance	0.614	0.617	0.05	12.228	0
Workplace Harassment -> Personal or Organizational Deviance	0.205	0.207	0.073	2.785	0.006
Workplace Harassment -> Self-Efficacy	0.228	0.223	0.092	2.489	0.013
Workplace Ostracism -> Personal or Organizational Deviance	-0.045	-0.048	0.082	0.548	0.584
Workplace Ostracism -> Self-Efficacy	0.112	0.122	0.087	1.287	0.199

From significance test, the researcher has studied path coefficients from β -values. From table 7 the β -coefficient of all the relations is positive except the relation between workplace ostracism and personal or organizational deviance whose β -coefficient is negative. All these values of paths coefficients indicate that workplace ostracism and sexual harassment both positively influence self-efficacy; workplace sexual harassment and self-efficacy positively influence organizational deviant behaviors while workplace ostracism has negative impact on deviant behaviors.

Further, T-test & P-test is used to determine the level of significance between the independent and the dependent variable. If the T-value is above ± 1.96 and P value is less than 0.05 then the relation between the variables is said to be significant while if the T-value is below ± 1.96 and p-value is above 0.05 then the relation between the variables is said to be insignificant. From Table 4.4.2, the researcher has interpreted the significance level of relation between the independent variables and dependent variable. From the t- test and p-value, it is found that self-efficacy and workplace sexual harassment have significant positive relation with personal or organizational deviance with t values greater than +1.96 and p value smaller than 0.05 ($t=12.228$, $p < 0.05$) and ($t=2.785$, $p < 0.05$) respectively. Similarly, workplace sexual harassment has significant positive relation with self-efficacy ($t=2.489$, $p < 0.05$). In contrary, workplace ostracism has insignificant relation with self-efficacy with t values smaller than +1.96 and p value greater than 0.05 ($t=0.548$, $p > 0.05$) and insignificant negative relation with personal or organizational deviance in the private banking sector of Pakistan.

Table 8
Coefficient of determination

Personal or Organizational Deviance	0.471	0.463
Self-Efficacy	0.101	0.093

		Direct Effects	Indirect Effects	LLCI	ULCI	
In 8, R ²	WPO → POD	0.0749	0.1471	-0.0174	0.1672	table
	WHO → POD	0.1753	0.1827	0.0703	0.2803	

denotes the coefficient of determination which shows how well the data fits a model. From multiple regression of independent variables under the presence of mediating effect, the researcher has analyzed that the impact of workplace ostracism and sexual harassment together has moderate impact on personal or organizational deviance that is up to 47.1% which is likely to be moderate due to significant relation of workplace sexual harassment with the mediator as well as dependent variable, whereas self-efficacy is explained up to 10.1% which is very weak in regression.

Table 9
Analysis of Mediation

From significance test results, the relation has been identified between the variables. In the table 9, the researcher has confirmed the direct and indirect effects of workplace ostracism and sexual harassment on personal or organizational deviance in presence or absence of self-efficacy. The direct effects of WPO on POD are extremely weak which is negligible due to different signs of LLCI and ULCI it is clear that their relation is insignificant indicating that there is no mediation and no significant relation between workplace ostracism and organizational deviance, while the relationship between WHO and POD is significant in both direct and indirect effects as the signs of both LLIC and UICI are same which indicates that there is partial mediation of self-efficacy in explaining organizational; deviant behaviors through sexual harassment.

Hypothesis Testing

From the t-test and p-test, since there is an insignificant relation between Workplace Ostracism (IV₁) and self-efficacy (M) and also an insignificant relation between Workplace Ostracism (IV₁) and Personal or Organizational Deviance (DV) so H₀₁ and H₀₂ both are accepted as there is no mediation or direct relation between the IV₁ and DV. While there is a significant positive relation between Workplace Sexual Harassment (IV₂) and self-efficacy (M) and also a significant relation between Workplace Sexual Harassment (IV₂) and Personal or Organizational Deviance (DV), so H₀₃ and H₀₄ are rejected considering there is partial mediation between the IV₂ and DV and they both are also in a direct relation with each other.

Table 10
Hypothesis Results

H ₀₁	Supported
H ₀₂	Supported
H ₀₃	Not Supported
H ₀₄	Not Supported

Conclusion

The result conducted from this research is that in the private banking sector of Pakistan, the employees are not much effected by how their supervisor is degrading them , they are still motivated and have self—belief in how they are performing but due to their self-respect they start gathering hatred against their supervisors, the respondents were sure for their proficiencies and understood the office politics due to which they were not stressed due to discourteous behavior of the employer or supervisor but they tend to have a deviant behavior for the organization in order to defend their image in further cases. While workplace sexual harassment did showcase a positive and significant relationship with self-efficacy which concludes that the women in Pakistan at workplace are not petrified anymore by their sexual harassment, instead they raise their voice against such supervisors who tend to sexually introduce themselves with the women employees. Also, may be due to women marches in Pakistan or social platforms for women power have brought up this confidence in women employees to not loss their self-confidence due to sexual abuse at workplace, instead they have learnt to stand against them which results in their deviant behavior against their supervisors or organization.

This research only includes the data from the private banking sector of Karachi, Pakistan and only women sexual harassment was considered at the workplace, and it does not include the perspective of the full population. Moreover, it is recommended to the employers to judge the leadership skills of the employees at the time of recruitment so they don't pressurize their team members or bully someone in the premises of the organization, also to stop the sexual harassment on women, proper camera security should be provided and no gents should be allowed to speak to women in loneliness. Simultaneously, a feedback should be taken from female employees to get information about their supervisors' behavior with them.

Since, this research has only been conducted under the private banking sector of Pakistan, so in future the data sample can be expanded top public sector and emotional exhaustion or job insecurity can be considered as mediator between these variables.

References

- A. Santos, J. R. (1999). Cronbach's Alpha: A Tool for Assessing the Reliability of Scales. *Journal of Extension* , 37 (02), 1-4.
- Abbas, M. R., Darr, W., & Bouckenooghe, D. (2014). Combined effects of perceived politics and psychological capital on job satisfaction, turnover intentions, and performance". *Journal of Management* , 40, 1813–1830.
- Agwa, A. M. (2018). Workplace Deviance Behaviors. *Leadership* .
- Ahmad, A., & Omar, Z. (2013). Abusive Supervision and Deviant Workplace Behavior: The Mediating Role of Work–Family Conflict. *The Journal of Human Resource and Adult Learning* , 9 (2), 124-130.
- Ahmad, A., & Safaria, T. (2013). Effects of Self-Efficacy on Students' Academic Performance. *Journal of Educational, Health and Community Psychology* , 2 (1), 22-29.
- Aksu, A. (2016). Organizational deviance and multi-factor leadership. *Educational Research and Reviews* , 11 (8).
- Alexander, J. S. (2007). Seven day self-esteem booster. *Hachette Children's Books* .
- Altman, D. G., & Head. (1997, February 22). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *General Practice* .
- Anila. (1998). Sexual Harassment at workplaces and coping strategies employed by women. . *Department of Psychology* , 209.
- Aquino, K., Lewis, M. U., & Bradfield, M. (1999). Justice Constructs, Negative Affectivity, and Employee Deviance: A Proposed Model and Empirical Test. *Journal of Organizational Behavior* , 20 (7), 1073-1091.

- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, , 84 (2), 191.
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory.
- Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*. 17 (1), 99-120.
- Borsboom, D. M. (2004). *The concept of validity*. *Psychological Review* (4 ed., Vol. 111).
- Cakirpaloglu, S., Āech, T., & Kvintova, J. (2018). The impact of workplace bullying on self-esteem among elementary school teachers. *Conference paper* .
- Chen, Y., & Li, S. (2019). The Relationship Between Workplace Ostracism and Sleep Quality: A Mediated Moderation Model. *Frontiers in Psychology* , 10, 319.
- Choi, Y. (2020). A study of the influence of workplace ostracism on employees' performance: moderating effect of perceived organizational support. *EJMBE* , 29 (3), 333-345.
- Christopher, U., & Amy, B. (2004). Sexual Harassment as a Gendered Expression of Power. *American Sociological Review*. , 69, 64–92.
- Chung, Y. W., & Yang, J. Y. (2017). The mediating effects of organization-based self-esteem for the relationship between workplace ostracism and workplace behaviors. *Baltic Journal of Management* , 12 (2).
- Colbert, A., Mount, M., Harter, J., Witt, L., & Barrick, M. (2004). Interactive effects of personality and perceptions of the work situation on workplace deviance. *Journal of Applied Psychology* , 89 (4), 599-609.
- Cropanzano, R. (1998). Emotional Exhaustion as a Predictor of Job Performance and Voluntary Turnover. *Journal of Applied Psychology* , 83 (3), 486-493.
- Dannenbaum, T., & Jayaram, K. (2005). Combating sexual harassment at the work place: A handbook for wŃwŃeŃ, eŃwŃpŃloyers aŃd NGO's. *India Centre for Humans Rights and Law* .
- Demir, M. (2009). Konaklama iŃletmelerinde duygusal zeka, ŃrgŃtsel sapma, alıŃma yaŃamı kalitesi ve iŃten ayrılma eęilimi arasındaki iliŃkinin analizi. Dokuz EylŃl Ńniversitesi,. *Sosyal Bilimler EnstitŃsŃ* .
- Dirk, D. C., Haq, I. U., & Azeem, M. U. (2019). Workplace ostracism and job performance: Roles of self-efficacy and job level. *Personnel Review* , 48 (1), 184-203.
- Donahue, E. G., Forest, J., Vallerand, R. J., Lemyre, P. N., Braud, L. C., & Bergeron, Ē. (2012). Passion for Work and Emotional Exhaustion: The Mediating Role of Rumination and Recovery. *APPLIED PSYCHOLOGY: HEALTH AND WELL-BEING* , 4 (3), 341–368.
- Dos, D. E., Kumar, M. M., & Pavan, M. (2014). A Study On Sexual Harassment Among Women Workers At Work Place In Velore City. *Social Science* , 4 (12), 35-37.
- Eisenberger, R., Armeli, S., Rexwinkel, B., Lynch, P. D., & Rhoades, L. (2001). Reciprocation of perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology* , 86 (1), 42-51.
- Enwereuzor, I., Onyishi, I., Onyebueke, I., Amazue, L., & Nwoke. (2017). Personality as a moderator between emotional exhaustion and workplace deviance among teachers. *Journal of Psychology in Africa* , 27 (1), 41-46.
- Ermann, M. D., & Lundman, R. J. (1978). Deviant Acts by Complex Organizations: Deviance and Social Control at the Organizational Level of Analysis. *Sociol. Q.* , 19 (1), 55-67.
- Fatima, T., Ilyas, M., Rehman, C. A., & Imran, M. K. (2017). Empirical Investigation of Relationship between Workplace Ostracism and Employee Silence: A Test of Mediating Effects of Self-Esteem and

- Meaningful Existence in Context of Public Sector Universities in Punjab. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences* , 10 (1).
- Ferris, D. L., Brown, D. J., Berry, J. W., & Lian, H. (2008). The development and validation of the workplace ostracism scale. *Journal of Applied Psychology* , 93, 1348-1366.
- Fiset, J., Al-Hajj, R., & Vongas, J. G. (2017). Workplace Ostracism Seen through the Lens of Power. *Frontiers in Psychology* .
- Fiset, J., Hajj, R. A., & Vongas, J. G. (2017). Workplace Ostracism Seen through the Lens of Power. *Front. Psychol.*
- Frederico, G., Kumar, V., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2021). Impact of the Strategic Sourcing Process on the Supply Chain Response to the COVID-19 effects. *Business Process Management Journal* , 1-29.
- Gillaspie, D. (2018, February 13). *How the #MeToo movement is affecting your leadership (and you might not.* Retrieved December 21, 2020, from Forbes: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2018/02/13/how-the-metoo-movement-is-affecting-your-leadership-and-you-might-not-even-notice/#1637318665fe>
- Giunipero, L. C., Denslow, D., & Eltantawy, R. (2005). Purchasing/supply chain management flexibility: Moving to an entrepreneurial skill set. *Industrial Marketing Management* , 602 – 613.
- Hair, J., Hult, G., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM).
- Hao, S., Hong, W., Xu, H., Zhou, L., & Xie, Z. Relationship between resilience, stress and burnout among civil servants in Beijing, China: mediating and moderating effect analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences* , 83, 65-71.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C., & Sinkovics, R. (2009). *J. Acad. Market. Sci* , 20, 227–319.
- Hitlan, R. (2009). The influence of workplace exclusion and personality on counterproductive work behaviours: an interactionist perspective. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* , 18 (4), pp. 477-502.
- Houle, J. N., Staff, J., Mortimer, J. T., Uggen, C., & Blackstone, A. (2011). The Impact of Sexual Harassment on Depressive symptoms during the early occupational career, *Soc Ment Health* . , 1 (2), 89–105.
- Howladar, M. H., Rahman, S., & Uddin, A. (2018). Deviant Workplace Behavior and Job Performance: The Moderating Effect of Transformational Leadership. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies (IJMS)* , 11 (1).
- Hsieh, Y. H., Wang, H. H., & Ma, S. C. (2019). The mediating role of self-efficacy in the relationship between workplace bullying, mental health and intention to leave among nurses in Taiwan. *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health* , 32 (2), 245 – 254.
- Hussain, T., & Asif, S. (2012). Is employees' turnover intention driven by organizational commitment and perceived organizational support? *Journal of Quality and Technology Management* , 8, 1-10.
- Jahanzeb, S., & Fatima, T. (2018). How Workplace Ostracism Influences Interpersonal Deviance: The Mediating Role of Defensive Silence and Emotional Exhaustion. *Journal of Business and Psychology* , 33, 779–791.
- Jamal, M. (1985). Relationship of job stress to job performance: A study of managers and blue-collar workers. *Human Relations* , 38, 409–424.
- Jiang, H., Jiang X, X., Sun, P., & Li, X. (2020). Coping with workplace ostracism: the roles of emotional exhaustion and resilience in deviant behavior. *Management Decision* .

- Johnson, P. A., Widnall, S. E., & Benya, F. F. (2018). Sexual Harassment of Women: Climate, Culture, and Consequences in Academic Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. *The National Academies Press* , 23-50.
- Jones, E. E., Carter-Sowell, A. R., Kelly, J. R., & Williams, K. D. (2009). 'I'm out of the loop': Ostracism through information exclusion. *Group Processes and Intergroup Relations* , 12, 157–174.
- Kanu, H. (2022, Feb 17). *After five years of #MeToo movement, a modest win for women's workplace rights*. Retrieved May 18, 2022, from Reuters: <https://www.reuters.com/legal/transactional/after-five-years-metoo-movement-modest-win-womens-workplace-rights-2022-02-16/>
- Khurram, S. (2009). Perceived organizational support, antecedents and consequences proposing and testing a model in a public sector university of Pakistan. *South Asian Journal of Management* , 16, 7–26.
- Kim, S. T., Lee, H.-H., & Hwang, T. (2020). Logistics integration in the supply chain: a resource dependence theory perspective. *International Journal of Quality Innovation* , 6 (5).
- Kura, K. M., Faridawahti, M., & Chauhan, A. (2015). Does Self-Regulatory Efficacy Matter? Effects of Punishment Certainty and Punishment Severity on Organizational Deviance. *Sage Open* , 1-14.
- Lazarus, R., & Folkman, S. (1984). Stress, Appraisal and Coping.
- Liao, H., Joshi, A., & Chuang, A. (2004). Sticking out like a sore thumb: Employee dissimilarity and deviance at work. *Personnel Psychology* , 57, 969–1000.
- Lima, L. F. (2018). Ostracized Employees In the Workplace: The Relationship Between Ostracism And Self-efficacy. *Tilburg University* .
- Liu, J., Kwan, H. K., Lee, C., & Hui, C. (2013). Work-to-family spillover effects of workplace ostracism: The role of work-home segmentation preferences. *Human Resource Management* , 52, 75–94.
- Loeb, C. (2016). Self-efficacy at work, social, emotional and cognitive dimesions. *School of Health, Care and Social Welfare* .
- Malik, M. S., Sattar, S., Younas, S., & Nawaz, M. K. (2019). *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research* , 8 (1), 33-50.
- Manogharan, G., Wysk, R. A., & Harrysson, O. L. (2012). Measuring manufacturing performance with the implementation of TPM: an exploratory study. *Int. J. Productivity and Quality Management* , 9 (4), 456-471.
- Maslach, Christina, & Susan, E. J. (1981). The Measurement of Experienced Burnout. *Journal of Occupational* , 2 (2), 99–113.
- McBrier, D. B., & Wilson, G. (2004). Going Down?: Race and Downward Occupational Mobility for White-Collar Workers in the 1990s. *SAGE Journals* , 31 (3), 283-322.
- Mikkelsen, E. G., & Einarsen, S. (2002). Relationships between exposure to bullying at work and psychological and psychosomatic health complaints: The role of state negative affectivity and generalized self-efficacy. *Scand J Psychol* , 43 (5), 397-405.
- Morrison, E. W. (2014). Employee voice and silence. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychoogy and Organizaional Behavior* , 1 (1), 173-197.
- Naqvi. (2009). Competency mapping and managing talent. *Insfain Journal of Management Reviews* , 8 (1), 85-94.
- Nauman, B., & Abbasi, A. S. (2014). Sexual Harassment at Workplace... A Case of Banking Sector in Lahore. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* , 20 (5), 558-566.
- Ng, T. H., & Feldman, D. C. (2012). Employee voice behavior: A meta-analytic test of the conservation of resources framework. *Journal of Organizational Behavior* , 33, 216–234.

- Nielsen, M. B., Madsen, I. E., Clausen, T., Skov, S. S., Kjær, S., Kvorning, L. V., et al. (2019). Sexual harassment at work: Design of a new questionnaire to measure sexual harassment. *European Journal of Public Health* , 29.
- O'Neill, T., Lewis, R., & Carswell, J. (2011). Employee personality, justice perceptions, and the prediction of workplace deviance. *Personality Individual Diff.* , 51 (5), 595-600.
- Omosa, R. J. (2005). Procurement Performance Measurement Systems: A Survey of large manufacturing companies in Nairobi.
- Paracha, M. U., & Shahzad, K. (2017). Work place bullying on deviant work Behavior among nurses in Pakistan: Mediating role of interpersonal conflict. *Pakistan Business Review* .
- Park, A. (2017, October 24). #MeToo reaches 85 countries with 1.7M tweets. Retrieved December 21, 2020, from CBS News: <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/metoo-reaches-85-countries-with-1-7-million-tweets/>
- Peng, A., & Zeng, W. (2017). Workplace ostracism and deviant and helping behaviors: the moderating role of 360 degree feedback. *Journal of Organizational Behavior* , 38 (6), 833-855.
- Rabbi, F., Ahad, N., Kousar, T., & Ali, T. (2015). Talent Management as a Source of Competitive Advantage. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy* , 5 (9), 208-214.
- Raykov, T. (1997). Estimation of Composite Reliability for Congeneric Measures. *Applied Psychological Measurement* .
- Robinson, S. L., & Bennett, R. J. (1995). A typology of deviant workplace behaviors: A multidimensional scaling study. *Academy of Management Journal* , 38 (2), 555-572.
- Roscigno, V. J. (2019). Discrimination, Sexual Harassment, and the Impact of Workplace Power. *Socius: Sociological Research for a Dynamic World* , 5 (21), 1-21.
- Rosenberg, M. (1965). Society and the adolescent self-image. *Princeton University Press* .
- Samiullah. (2019). Impact of Workplace Bullying on Workplace Deviant Behaviors: The Mediating Role of Negative A of Internal Locus of Control. *Faculty of Management & Social Sciences* .
- Santos, A. J., & Reynaldo. (1999). Cronbach's Alpha: A Tool for Assessing the Reliability of Scales. *Journal of Extension* , 37 (02), 1-4.
- Sarwar, A., Abdullah, M. I., Sarfraz, M., & Imran, M. K. (2019). Collaborative effect of workplace ostracism and self-efficacy versus job stress. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Management and Innovation* .
- Schat, A., & Kelloway, E. (2005). Workplace aggression. *Handbook of Work Stress* , 189-218.
- Shetty, A. P., & V, N. B. (2017). Workplace Harassment among employees: An exploratory study. *Archives of Medicine and Health Sciences* , 5, 187-90.
- Siegel, R. (2003). A Short History of Sexual Harassment. *Directions in Sexual Harassment Law* , 1 (4), 1-39.
- Taber, K. S. (2016). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing. *Res Sci Educ* .
- Tarkkonen, L. J., & I., K. V. (2005). Measurement errors in multivariate measurement scales. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis* , 96 (1), 172-189.
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011 , June 2). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education* .
- Tepper, B., Henle, C., Lambert, L., Giacalone, R., & Duffy, M. (2008). Abusive supervision and subordinates' organization deviance . *Journal of Applied Psychology* , 93 (4).
- Thau, D. M., Workman, K. M., Dijke, M. V., & Cremer, D. D. (2011). Leader mistreatment, employee hostility, and deviant behaviors: Integrating self-uncertainty and thwarted needs perspectives on deviance. *Elsevier Inc.*

- Uzhakina. (2007, July 12). *A cadre of talent and talent management*. Retrieved from Training.ru: <http://www.trainings.ru/library/>
- Visinskaite, V. (2015). Workplace Bullying: in relation to Self-Esteem, Stress, Life Satisfaction and Cyberbullying. *Dublin Business School* .
- Wann-Yih, W., Chwan-Yi, C., Ya-Jung, W., & Hui-Ju, T. (2004). The influencing factors of commitment and business integration on supply chain management. *Industrial Management & Data Systems* , 322 - 333.
- Waseem, M. (2016). Deviant Workplace Behaviors in Organizations in Pakistan. *The Lahore Journal of Business* , 4 (2), 93–104.
- Wilde, N., & Hsu, A. (2019). The influence of general self-efficacy on the interpretation of vicarious experience information within online learning. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* , 16 (26), 1-20.
- William, K. D. (2001). Ostracism: The Power of Silence. *Emotions and Social Behavior*.
- Willness, C., Steel, P., & Lee, K. (2007). A Meta-analysis of the antecedents and consequences of workplace sexual harassment. *Personnel Psychology* , 60 (1), 127-162.
- Wilson, G. (1997). Pathways to Power: Racial Differences in the. *Social Problems* , 44, 801–817.
- Wu, L., Yim, F. K., Kwan, H. K., & Zhang, X. (2012). Coping with workplace ostracism: The roles of ingratiation and political skill in employee psychological distress. *Journal of Management Studies* , 49, 178–199.
- Yoo, J. (2013). Exploring The Impact of Social Undermining on Salesperson Deviance: An Integrated Model. *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management* , 79–90.
- Yusuf, M. (2011). The impact of self-efficacy, achievement motivation, and selfregulated learning strategies on students' academic achievement. *Procedia Social and Behavioral* , 15, 2623–2626.
- Zhang, S., Chen, G., & Chen, G. (2008). Interpersonal and collective group identities: Differential contribution to business security. *CIBER* .

APENDIX- Survey Questionnaire

Student of Greenwich University are working on Final Project of Research on “*The Impact of Workplace Sexual Harassment among Women and Workplace Ostracism on Personal or Organizational Deviance with the mediating effect of Self- Efficacy*”. Its primary data is supposed to be collected from the employees working in private banking sector of Pakistan. So, you are requested to cooperate in this collection of data in which your participation will be highly appreciated. Please fill this questionnaire.

Gender:

- Male
 Female

Age Group:

- 21 to 25 years
 26 to 30 years
 31 to 35 years
 36 to 40 years
 41 and Above

Qualification:

- Under Matric

Income Group:

- Below 20,000

Experience:

- Less than 1 year

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Matric | <input type="radio"/> 20,000-30,000 | <input type="radio"/> 1-3 years |
| <input type="radio"/> Intermediate | <input type="radio"/> 30,000-40,000 | <input type="radio"/> 4 to 6 years |
| <input type="radio"/> Bachelors | <input type="radio"/> 40,000-50,000 | <input type="radio"/> 7 to 9 years |
| <input type="radio"/> Post-Graduate | <input type="radio"/> 50,000-60,000 | <input type="radio"/> 10 years or above |
| | <input type="radio"/> Above 60,000 | |

The Impact of Workplace Sexual Harassment among Women and Workplace Ostracism on Personal or Organizational Deviance with the mediating effect of Self- Efficacy	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Workplace Ostracism (Fiset, Al-Hajj, & Vongas, Workplace Ostracism Seen through the Lens of Power, 2017)					
1. I feel excluded from team discussions					
2. I never get appreciation for what I do					
3. My skills are usually neglected by my supervisor					
4. My boss don't treat all the team members equally					
5. My ideas are usually rejected					
Workplace Sexual Harassment (Nielsen, et al., 2019)					
1. I feel uncomfortable around my supervisor					
2. I usually feel unwanted physical contact					
3. I usually get favors from my supervisor without any reason					
4. My supervisor treats me differently when I'm alone					
5. I am usually admired for my physical appearance					
Self-Efficacy (Loeb, 2016)					
1. I always express my opinion when my supervisor disagrees with me					
2. I trust in my skills					
3. I openly speak about my ideas					
4. I never compromise my self-respect in any case					

Personal or Organizational Deviance (Agwa, 2018)

1. I usually act rudely at workplace					
2. I usually leave early					
3. I usually act sick to get halftime					
4. I usually curse my boss with my peers					